

Some Metal-Selenourea Complexes*

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Selenourea complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II), Cu(I), Ag(I) and Tl(I) have been prepared and their infrared spectra have been interpreted. In all the cases selenium atom of the selenourea is coordinated to the metal atom.

Thiourea and substituted thioureas are well-known to form complexes with transition and post-transition metal ions. The coordination tendencies of thiourea and urea are extremely at variance though the molecules may appear to be structurally alike. Thus, urea coordinates through N atom as well as O atom whereas, only sulphur ligancy is proved in metal-thiourea complexes. Recently some isostructural thiourea and selenourea complexes of transition metal thiocyanates have been reported¹. This paper deals with the isolation of several metal-selenourea complexes and their spectral characteristics.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fluka reagent grade selenourea (Su) was made use of in all the preparations. Required amount of selenourea solution was added to the metal salt solutions. The overall pH of the solutions was maintained at 2, otherwise, elemental selenium precipitates out. The resultant

TABLE I

Analytical data of the Complexes

Compound		C	H	N	Cl	M
		%				
[Cu 3 Su] ₂ SO ₄	Found	7.38	2.57	17.92	—	13.43
	Required	7.50	2.52	17.50	—	13.22
[Zn 4 Su] ₂ SO ₄	Found	7.26	2.53	17.38	—	10.33
	Required	7.35	2.47	17.50	—	10.01
[Cd 4 Su] SO ₄	Found	6.67	2.18	16.32	—	15.88
	Required	6.86	2.30	16.00	—	16.04
[Ag.2 Su]ClO ₄	Found	5.44	1.65	12.62	7.68	23.93
	Required	5.39	1.78	12.40	7.82	23.80
[Ag.3 Su]NO ₃	Found	6.76	2.33	18.08	—	19.98
	Required	6.69	2.25	18.20	—	20.03
[Zn.2 Su (NCS) ₂]	Found	11.08	2.01	19.48	—	15.41
	Required	11.20	1.89	19.60	—	15.30
[Tl.4 Su]Cl	Found	6.46	2.27	15.21	4.96	27.81
	Required	6.56	2.18	15.32	4.85	27.92

* Work carried out at Anorg. Chem. Institut, Göttingen, West Germany.

solution was heated on a water bath for few minutes and cooled. Colourless crystals obtained were filtered and washed with acetone. In the case of copper complex, Cu(II) was first reduced to Cu(I) which complexed with the excess selenourea to give colourless crystals similar to that of thiourea. The analytical values are given in Table 1.

The infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 225 spectrophotometer using nujol emulsion and CsI pellet techniques. In the far-infrared region the spectra were run on polyethylene plates using nujol emulsions. The characteristic frequencies are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Principal infrared frequencies of selenourea and its complexes

Su	[Cu.3Su] SO ₄	[Zn.4Su] SO ₄	[Cd.4Su] SO ₄	[Ag.2Su] ClO ₄	[Ag.3Su] NO ₃	[Zn.2Su. (NCS) ₂]	[Tl.4Su] Cl	Assignment
3350(s)	3360(s)	3360(s)	3380(s)	3370(s)	3370(s)	3380(sh)	3360(s)	
3260(s)	3280(s)	3270(s)	3300(s)	3270(s)	3270(s)	3360(s)	3250(s)	NH ₂ stretch
3100(s)	3190(s)		3080(s)	3180(s)	3170(s)	3280(s)	3140(s)	
	3125(m)					3180(s)		
1605(s)	1650(s)	1636(s)	1630(s)	1608(s)	1610(s)	1638(s)	1610(s)	NH ₂ bend
	1600(s)	1610(s)				1610(s)		
1482(m)	1460(s)	1410(sh)	1516(w)	1482(m)	1482(m)	1512(m)	1480(m)	N-C-N stretch ⁺
1473(m)	1352(s)	1400(s)	1378(s)	1382(s)	1378(s)	1410(sh)	1410(s)	NH ₂ rock +
1398(s)						1390(s)	1380(m)	C = Se stretch
1090(m)	*	*	*	*	1090(w)	1095(w)	1100(w)	N-C-N-stretch + NH ₂ rock
733(w)	725(w)	730(w)	720(w)	720(w)	720(sh)	718(w)	715(w)	C=Se stretch + N-C-N-stretch
578(m)	586(s)	570(sh)	532(w)	575(m)	580(m)	545(s)	575(w)	N-C-N-deforma- tion .
392(m)	390(m)	380(m)	392(m)	382(m)	382(m)	372(m)	378(m)	N-C-Se deforma- tion.
—	280(s)	272(s)	262(s)	262(s)	258(s)	258(s)	276(s)	M-Se stretch.

* masked by the anion absorption.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The complexes are insoluble in most of the common solvents such as ethylacetate, alcohol, chloroform, carbontetrachloride etc. Aqueous solutions of the complexes were found to slowly deposit elemental selenium. The complexes decomposed at about 150°. On keeping in a glass container, red selenium is found to deposit on the sides of the glass.

The i.r. spectrum of the selenourea is similar to that of thiourea². Bands in the 3100–3400 cm⁻¹ region are associated with NH bands. If coordination occurs through N atom in the complexes these bands split and decrease in intensity. This does not appear to happen so that bonding through selenium can be inferred in all cases.

The bands in the region 1400, 1100 and 700 cm^{-1} are due to the mixing of NCN stretching, NH_2 rocking the CSe stretching modes. Coordination through Se will lead to a decrease in the CSe stretching frequency and an increase in NCN stretching frequency. The 1400 and 700 cm^{-1} bands lowered on coordination but the 1100 cm^{-1} decreased in intensity with a slight increase in frequency. Due to strong absorption of SO_4 and ClO_4 groups in this region this could not be noticed in the sulphate and perchlorate complexes. The strong band around 260 cm^{-1} is assigned to M-Se stretching frequency³. Thus, from the spectral frequencies it is clear that M-Se bond is formed in all the complexes.

The strong and broad absorption band around 1100 cm^{-1} and a strong absorption around 620 cm^{-1} followed by a weak absorption at 940 cm^{-1} for the sulphate and perchlorate complexes indicate the T_d symmetry of these groups. In $[\text{Ag}_3\text{Su}]\text{NO}_3$ a strong intensity band at 1412 and a weak band at 820 cm^{-1} indicates that the NO_3 group is ionic. The strong band at 2075 followed by a weak band at 802 cm^{-1} observed for $[\text{Zn}_2\text{Su}(\text{NCS})_2]$ are due to CN and CS stretching frequencies of N-bonded-NCS group.

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